

PROCEDURE, OBJECTIVES AND TASKS OF PROMOTING WORK EXPERIENCE OF ADVANCED TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In the article, the procedure, goals and means of popularization of advanced work of teachers are developed. The necessity of improving the quality of education through the use of advanced pedagogical experiences in education has been highlighted.*

Keywords: *pedagogical experience, innovation, innovative technology, pedagogical activity, pedagogical production, educational trends, research skills, modern, advanced.*

The source of pedagogical creativity is advanced pedagogical experience. Advanced pedagogical experience is rich in problematic situations. By advanced pedagogical experience, we understand the teacher's creative approach to his pedagogical task, searching for new, modern, effective, and the most suitable ways and tools in the education of students. Advanced pedagogical experience forms and methods of work used by the teacher, methods and tools, and innovative technologies. To study advanced pedagogical experience, to discover new pedagogical phenomena and laws based on it, to make good, quality changes in the educational process, to manage students' cognitive activities, to solve the problems of modeling the educational process in a new way. A teacher who works creatively can only successfully teach and educate. Advanced teachers must also have research skills and abilities to analyze their work experience. An advanced teacher always strives to learn new things in the field of pedagogy, he tries to use the experiences of other teachers and to summarize his own personal experiences. It requires to be able to think freely about it, to be able to convey the achievements of science to students, and finally, to be able to teach students to think creatively and do research. Therefore, it is necessary for a teacher, first of all, to acquire research skills. The teacher collects, analyzes and draws conclusions based on the experiences of scientists during his research activities. In the process of using science conclusions in his practical work, he acquires very important qualities necessary for a modern teacher. Advanced teachers' pay special attention to the choice of teaching methods [1]

It is very important to expand and deepen the content of education and its content, to include in this content not only knowledge, skills, qualifications, but also the experience of creative activities that make up universal human culture, and relationships with the environment. Advanced pedagogical and social experiences are an important factor in the formation of pedagogical skills. The main aspect of new pedagogical technologies is the need to re-create school textbooks at a high level. The creation of textbooks should be based on many years of scientific, cultural, aesthetic, and spiritual experiences. Pedagogical activity in the educational process has a creative character according to its work. It is known that creativity is needed only when a person faces a problem. Teaching activity has such characteristics. The main essence of pedagogical creativity is clearly defined by the purpose and character of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical activity is the process of solving innumerable pedagogical issues that depend on a person's personality, worldview, beliefs, consciousness, and attitude. Creativity in the teacher's activity is expressed in the methods of solving these problems, in his ability to find ways to solve them.

The order of the Minister of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 32 dated February 7, 2024 was approved. It is necessary to improve the procedure for popularizing the advanced experience of teachers and the modern methods they use during their activities about. [2]

This Regulation determines the procedure for popularizing the advanced experience and modern methods used by teachers in the preschool and school education system, as well as studying and popularizing the advanced work experience of experienced pedagogical personnel in the preschool and school education system, including science teachers. The Department of Methodological Services at the Republican Education Center under the Ministry of Pre-school and School Education and the National Centers for Training Teachers in New Methodologies is a coordinating working body for studying and popularizing the best practices of teachers. This popularization procedure is applied to general secondary school, Presidential, specialized and creative schools, special boarding schools, and teachers of loving schools and is optional. It consists of the effective organization of the educational process in the general secondary education system and the introduction of advanced practices aimed at improving the quality of education, modern pedagogical technologies, and the establishment of mutual experience exchange between the employees of the preschool and school education system. Best practices recommended for popularization should be in the form of a methodical guide or methodical recommendation. Methodological works that are not in the form of a methodical guide or methodical recommendation and have been popularized over the past years will not be studied. Methodological works are publicized at the following levels: at the school level, at the district (city) level, at the regional level, at the republic level. If found, it is recommended to the Pedagogical Council of the school for dissemination at the school level. Based on the recommendation of the Methodological Association, the Pedagogical Council examines whether the applicant's methodological work has been developed in accordance with the requirements and evaluation criteria of the methodological work approved by this order, and the Pedagogical Council makes a decision on whether or not to popularize it at the school level. If the methodological work of the applicant is given a positive conclusion and is considered worthy of dissemination, it will be disseminated at the school level by the decision of the Pedagogical Council and will be placed on the platform ommazhartan.uz and sent to the next stages. In this case, the following documents are placed by the applicant on the platform of ommazhartan.uz: an electronic (pdf) copy of the decision of the Pedagogical Council that the methodological work was given a positive conclusion and publicized at the level of the educational institution, a methodical work recommended for dissemination (an electronic (pdf) copy of the methodical manual or methodological recommendation, a reference letter (letter) and a copy of a diploma in the field of specialization. Dissemination at the district (city) and region (Tashkent city, Republic of Karakalpakstan) level: methodical work sent through the disseminating.uz platform was studied by the Educational Methodological Council of the Department of Methodological Services. The methodical work of the applicant is evaluated with a maximum of 80 points. Methodological works evaluated with 80 points are considered popularized at the regional level (Tashkent city, Republic of Karakalpakstan).

Minister of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Order No. 32 of February 7, 2024 of the "On improving the procedure for popularizing the advanced experience and modern methods used by teachers during their work" information was prepared in the section of districts.

1. The number of assigned cases in the Bukhara region is divided into districts

- Bukhara
- Bukhara district
- Shofirkon district
- Jondor district
- Peshku district
- G'ijduvon district
- Vobkent district
- Olot district
- Korakul district
- Romitan district
- Korovulbozor district
- Kogon district
- Kogon

Loaded methodological works on platform Ommalastirish.uz

2. Loaded jobs are a percentage of the total number of teachers in the district

Methodological works uploaded on the Ommalastirish.uz platform are compared to the total number of pupils in the districts

- Bukhara
- Bukhara district
- Shofirkon district
- Jondor district
- Peshku district

- Gijduvan district
- Vobkent district
- Olot district
- Korakul district
- Romitan district
- Korovulbozor district
- Kogon district
- Kogon

3. The number of applications received for physics in the Bukhara region

- Promotion
- Bukhara
- Bukhara district
- Shofirkon district
- Jondor district
- Peshku district
- Gijduvan district
- Vobkent district
- Olot district
- Korakul district
- Romitan district
- Korovulbozor district
- Kogon district
- Kogon

Total Percentage

4. Loaded work is a percentage of the total number of teachers in the district

Kogon

Korovulbozor district

Korakul district

Vobkent district

Peshku district

Shofirkon Bukhara

In conclusion, it can be said that the main goal of improving the popularization of teachers' advanced experience and modern methods used during their activities is to further improve the quality of education through the exchange of experience and the use of advanced pedagogical experiences in education. It should also be said that the main and great task before us today is to bring up a mature and well-rounded person.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining “Xalq ta’limi tizimida ta’lim sifatini baholash sohasidagi xalqaro tadqiqotlarni tashkil etish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida” 2018-yil 8-dekabrda 997-sonli qarori [1]
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi vazirligining buyrug‘i. O‘qituvchilarning ilg‘or tajribasi va faoliyat davomida qo‘llab kelayotgan zamonaviy metodikalarini ommalashtirish tartibini takomillashtirish to‘g‘risida. Toshkent sh.2024-yil 7-fevral, 32-son.[2]